

characteristics of these species differ. We undertook to more completely characterize strains reported as *P. glumae* found in Latin America. We also compared the characteristics of the two species to clarify some discrepancies in published descriptions.

Three strains of a nonfluorescent pathogenic bacterium obtained from discolored rice grains collected from farmers' fields in Colombia were compared with four culture collection strains of *P. glumae* and 25 strains of *P. avenae* (6 culture collection strains and 19 strains previously identified at CIAT), using standard bacteriological techniques. The culture collection strains included type specimens of each species.

The pathogenic strains recovered from discolored grains were consistent with *P. glumae*, rather than with *P. avenae* (see table). All strains tested could be distinguished from *Erwinia herbicola* in that they did not grow anaerobically and had multiple polar flagella. However, some differences were observed among the field-collected strains and the strains of known identity, as well as differences from published characteristics of the species.

The original description of *P. glumae* referred to it as producing a fluorescent pigment on potato agar. This probably referred to the diffusible green nonfluorescent pigment that we and others have observed to be produced by some, but not

all strains. The growth limit for *P. glumae* has been reported to be 40 °C; however, the strains in this study all grew at 41°C.

Researchers in the U.S., in establishing the synonymy of *P. alboprecipitans* and *P. setaria* with *P. avenae* (*P. menae* is now considered to be the correct name for this pathogen), described their strains as oxidase negative. More recently, researchers in Japan described their strains as oxidase positive. We have found our strains to be oxidase positive.

The Japanese researchers also reported that their strains grew in 3% NaCl but not in 5% NaCl. Our strains grew in 5% NaCl. The Japanese reported negative tobacco hypersensitivity, lipase, and H₂S production. Our strains were positive, negative, and variable, respectively. The strains we identified as *P. avenae* and *P. glumae* also abundantly accumulated poly-b-hydroxybutyrate crystals. ■

Phenotypic characteristics^a three *Pseudomonas* strains that cause grain discoloration and sterility in Colombian ricefields compared to strains of *P. glumae* and *P. avenae*.

Phenotypic character	<i>P. glumae</i> (4 strains)	Colombian strain			<i>P. avenae</i> (25 strains)
		1445-4-1	1445-4-2	1462-7-2	
Fluorescent pigment	-	-	-	-	-
Arginine dihydrolase	-	+	+	+	+
Nitrate reduction	-	-	-	-	+
Oxidase	-	+	+	-	-
Diffusible green pigment	d (50)	+	+	-	-
Accumulation of poly-b-hydroxybutyrate crystals	+	+	+	+	+
Utilization for growth					
Arabinose	+	+	+	+	d (60)
Cellobiose	+	+	+	+	-
Raffinose	+	+	+	+	-
Sucrose	-	-	-	-	-
Xylose	d (75)	+	+	+	+
Adonitol	+	+	+	+	-
Inositol	+	+	+	+	-
Sorbitol	d (75)	-	-	-	+
Arginine	d (75)	+	+	+	-
Salicine	+	+	+	+	-
Acid from					
Dextrose	d (75)	+	+	+	+
Lactose	-	-	-	-	-
Sucrose	-	-	-	-	-
Mannitol	+	+	+	+	d (76)
H ₂ S from TSI	-	-	-	-	d (76)
Catalase	d (75)	+	+	+	+
Gelatin liquefaction	d (50)	+	+	+	-
Growth at 41°C	+	+	+	+	+
Growth in 5% NaCl	+	+	+	+	+
Indole	-	-	-	-	-
Lecithinase	+	+	+	+	-
Levan from sucrose	-	-	-	-	-
Lipase	-	-	-	-	-
Pit formation on CVP	-	-	-	-	-
Starch hydrolysis	-	-	-	-	+
Tobacco hypersensitivity	+	+	+	+	+
Pathogenicity on rice	+	+	+	+	+

^a + = 90% or more of strains positive, - = 90% or more of strains negative, d = 11-89% strains positive; number in parentheses is percent of strains positive.

False smut incidence on rice relative to plant characters and environmental factors

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We studied false smut *Ustilaginoidea virens* Tak. incidence on 32 rice cultivars and the relationship of disease severity to plant characters and ambient environmental factors in the 1987 dry season. Rice cultivars were dry seeded in upland conditions, in a completely randomized block design with three replications. False smut of panicles at maturity was recorded for each cultivar. Disease severity, infected panicles, and number of infected florets on the most infected panicle were recorded.

B3719C-TB-8-1-4, China 988, HPU2202, HPU5101, Nag 1-38, VL 501, and VRS1 were disease free. Disease severity on the 26 susceptible cultivars ranged from 1 to 17.9%. A significant negative correlation ($r = -0.54$) between plant height (range 70-135 cm) and disease severity indicated that short cultivars were more vulnerable than tall ones.

The correlation of disease severity and days to 50% flowering was not signifi-

Linear correlations of false smut (*Ustilagoidea virens*) disease incidence (percent panicles with false smut) on 32 rice cultivars and plant and environmental factors.

	Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>) ^a
Plant	
Plant height (cm)	-0.54*
Days to 50% flowering	0.095**
Environment ^a	
Maximum temp ^d (28.1°C)	-0.048
Minimum temp (20.1°C)	-0.040
Relative humidity (87.8%)	-0.321
Rainfall (1.4 mm)	-0.120
Cloudiness (1.74 h)	-0.176
Disease severity	
Number of false-smutted florets on the panicle with maximum infection	0.81*

^a P(0.05) = 0.349*. ^b Av of 32 d during flowering.

cant. Correlations with environmental factors during flowering (22 Aug-29 Sep) were negative and nonsignificant (see table).

Among cultivars, the positive correlation ($r = 0.81$) of number of smutted florets on the panicle with the most infected florets and percent false smutted panicles was significant. The relationship between number of smutted florets on the panicle with the most infected florets and percent panicles with false smut (regression coefficient $y = 1.26 + 0.763 x$) shows that, in assessing disease severity, one disease severity factor can be used to estimate another factor. ■

Bakanae and foot rot of rice in Punjab, Pakistan

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During a 1989 survey of rice crop diseases in Sialkot, Gujranwala, and Sheikhpura of Punjab Province, Basmati 385 growing in isolated farmers' fields showed symptoms similar to those of bakanae disease. Some of the plants had yellowish green, thin leaves and exhibited abnormal stem elongation, lower tillering, and rotting at the root-stem joint as well as at the first node.

Laboratory examination revealed the presence of *Fusarium moniliforme* Sheld., the imperfect stage of *Gibberella fijiikuroi* (identified on the basis of micro and macro conidia, micro conidiophores, and micro conidial chains). A pathogen-

icity test to fulfill the requirements of Koch's postulates confirmed *F. moniliforme* to be the causal organism.

This is the first report of this disease in Pakistan. ■

Efficacy of ethofenprox in preventing rice tungro (RTV) infection

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RTV transmitted by green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* is one of the important diseases of rice in many parts of India. We studied the efficacy of ethofenprox (a new ether-derived insecti-

cide similar to synthetic pyrethroids) against GLH and RTV transmission.

Potted TN1 plants in controlled greenhouse conditions were sprayed with ethofenprox. At 0.01%, ethofenprox killed 78% of confined viruliferous adults within 30 min; plants sprayed with 0.01% recorded significantly lower RTV infection than plants sprayed with 0.05% monocrotophos (see table). GLH mortality within 30 min and RTV transmission were related; GLH mortality after 30 min was not related to RTV transmission. ■

Effect of ethofenprox and monocrotophos on green leafhoppers and RTV transmission.^a

Insecticide	GLH mortality (%)				RTV infection (%)
	0.5 h	1.0 h	4.0 h	24 h	
Ethofenprox 0.01%	78 a	87 a	95 a	100 a	53 a
Monocrotophos 0.05%	22 b	58 a	93 a	100 a	80 b
Untreated control	0 c	0 b	0 b	2 b	100 c

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Integrated pest management—insects

Mutual interference among wolf spider adult females

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In ricefields, wolf spiders *Lycosa pseudoannulata* respond to high densities of prey, particularly brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål). This increases the chances that spiders will encounter each other while hunting for prey. That may decrease searching efficiency per predator and increase a tendency toward aggression, cannibalism, and outward dispersal. Such encounters between searching predators are often called "mutual interference."

We conducted laboratory experiments to measure mutual interference among wolf spiders and to determine the effect of hopper density on encounters between

spiders. Freshly emerged BPH adult females were placed inside mylar cages (19-cm diam, 55-cm ht) with 5 tillers of TN1 potted rice plants at densities of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 60 BPH/cage. They were exposed to 1, 2, or 3 freshly emerged adult female wolf spiders for 24 h. There were 5 replications.

Searching efficiency per spider, a , over the experimental period was computed as

$$a = 1/P \ln [N/(N-N_a)]$$

where a is searching efficiency, P is predator number, N is initial number of BPH, and N_a is number of BPH attacked. Log of a was plotted against log of P to obtain a linear regression. The resulting relationship of this linear model is

$$\log a = \log Q - m \log P$$

where Q and m are constants, characteristic of the predator.